
A Critical Study of The Landless Agriculture Labors in Tribal Communities in India

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Abstract:

The role which the landless agriculture labors play in the agricultural economy is very crucial and important because the availability of labor is a major constraint in the agricultural land use and cropping patterns of a region. Labor represents all human services other than decision making and capital. In the tribal area of North Maharashtra most of the peoples are landless. Landless agriculture Labors constitute the most neglected class in Indian Society. Their income is Low and employment is irregular. They are not organized and they cannot fight for their rights. researcher conducted a critical study of the social and economical conditions of Landless Agriculture Laborers in North Maharashtra. Labor is most important factor of the economy. A labor does a vital role in Indian economy. Labor is the main factor of production. Without labor any process of production should not be completed. Rather than that this major part of economy is ignored by our society. Labors and probably landless labors are facing lots of a problem in tribal area of North Maharashtra.

Landlessness is a also a big problem itself. Their poverty, their superstitious ness, and their illiteracy is the main reason of their difficulties. Up to 50 % of the Landless agriculture Labors are from tribal area. Most of the tribal area is still not connected with the world. Researcher will be study about their social and Economical conditions of tribal landless agriculture labors in North Maharashtra. Researcher will also find their problems. It will be helpful for that people to search new employment opportunities. It will be also helpful to Government to find out the solutions of all the landless agriculture labors in India.

Keyword - Tribal communities, Landlessness

Introduction:

Tribal communities in India, especially in remote areas, are among the most disadvantaged in terms of socio-economic status. They are the poorest in terms of income and human development and face multiple vulnerabilities. The situation is particularly dire among the most marginalized tribes. These communities lack access to resources and most of them are poor farmers and landless labourers. They have to depend on forests and other common property resources for their livelihood. However, access to various types of resources is declining. The productivity of their work is low and/or the remuneration they receive is negligible. Due to these reasons, the socio-economic status of tribal communities has deteriorated. Urgent steps are needed for their development and improvement of their living standards.

Historical Background of Tribals:

There are 427 Scheduled Tribes in India. According to the 1991 Census, their population is 7.8 percent of the total population. As a native of this country, Dr. Shalvin as well as Thakkar

Bappa had called them 'tribals'. Dr. Dhuryas refer to them as 'Backward Hindus'. They are also called 'Wild Castes' as they live in the forest. These groups are called "Scheduled Tribes" as notified by the provisions of Articles 341 and 342 of the Constitution of India. Scheduled Tribes are isolated and introverted groups and are homogenous in terms of production and consumption. People from this economically backward group are exploited by others. They differ from others in terms of language, caste, religion, and lifestyle.

Statement of the Problem:

“A Critical Study of Socio-Economic Conditions of Tribal Landless Agriculture Labours in North Maharashtra”

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the Concept of Landless Agriculture Labor of tribal area of North Maharashtra.
2. To study the Geographical area of North Maharashtra.
3. To take into account the prospects of tribal's the landless agriculture labor in North Maharashtra

Research Methodology:

The present study has used both primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected from 800 landless agriculture labors in tribal area of North Maharashtra.

Sources of Data:

Information was collected from Government's annual reports of the tribal area in North Maharashtra. Additionally, Various Magazines, Books and Articles were collected and studied from government offices.

Features of Tribal Landless Agricultural Laborers:

Some important features of agricultural laborers in India make them different from industrial laborers. Indian agricultural laborers are very different in economic, social and cultural background from workers in industrial and service sectors. In that case, the characteristics of agricultural laborers can be explained as follows.

Highest illiteracy: Indian agricultural laborers are largely illiterate. Due to this, illiteracy has increased. Due to high illiteracy, agricultural laborers are being exploited.

Scattered across the country: Agricultural laborers are found in every corner of the country. Wherever agriculture is done, these laborers are there. Moreover, they do not have to migrate much for work.

Unorganization: Since the scope of work of agricultural laborers is all over the country, organizations cannot be formed. Moreover, agricultural laborers are scattered in rural areas. They do not have enough financial strength to provide funds and time to organizations. Due to unorganization, the bargaining power of agricultural laborers remains low.

Nature and security of work: The agricultural labourer has to do any work in the farm. Moreover, he has to do different types of work every day. He is not given one type of work. Also, there is no security of work for this labourer. He is reduced from work at any time without any inquiry.

Confusion of wage rate and payment of wages: The wage rate of the agricultural labourer is low and the period of payment of wages is not fixed. Moreover, the wages are paid partly in money and partly in kind. Moreover, the wages are not paid as per the maximum wage rate.

Indebtedness: The agricultural labourer is constantly in debt. Therefore, he has to constantly borrow and borrow from the farmer. Therefore, the farmer hires him for low wages. Due to constant indebtedness, his bargaining power is destroyed.

Seasonal demand: The work that an agricultural worker gets is based on nature. When there is more rain, the number of workers required increases. Also, the demand for workers increases during the agricultural season. After the agricultural season is over, he has to remain unemployed.

Superstitious tendencies: Any Indian worker is a victim of superstition and superstition. Like industrial workers, agricultural workers are superstitious and believe in superstitions. Due to this, their actual wages remain low. Due to this, the standard of living of every agricultural worker is at a low level.

Difference in wage fixation: The wage fixation for agricultural workers is not the same. If you go to work for different farmers, there is a difference in the wages of each farmer. Similarly, every agricultural worker has to negotiate the wages when he changes the employer. Moreover, the wage fixation varies according to the season. There cannot be a uniform wage. Also, the principle of equal pay for equal work does not apply to agricultural workers. There is a difference in the wages of men and women.

Lack of means of struggle: Unlike industrial workers, agricultural labourers cannot strike to fight against their employers. Moreover, they cannot express their dissatisfaction against their employers. Because there is no security of work. Moreover, they do not have the numbers to strike and they do not have the time either.

Growth of Landless Agricultural Laborers:

The increasing number of labourers dependent on agriculture has led to an increase in the number of agricultural labourers, as is clear from the following table.

Statewise Landless Agricultural Laborers in India:

The table no. 1. provides data on the number of landless agricultural laborers in each state and union territory (UT) in India, based on the 2011 Census.

Table No. 1: Statewise Landless Agricultural Laborers in India

States/UTs	Total Landless agricultural labourers (Census 2011)
Jammu & Kashmir	5,47,705
Himachal Pradesh	1,75,038
Punjab	15,88,455
Chandigarh	1,687
Uttanchal	4,03,301
Haryana	15,28,133
Delhi	39,475
Rajasthan	49,39,664
Uttar Pradesh	1,99,39,223
Bihar	1,83,45,649
Sikkim	25,986
Arunachal Pradesh	36,171
Nagaland	62,962
Manipur	1,14,918
Mizoram	41,787

Tripura	3,53,618
Meghalaya	1,98,364
Assam	18,45,346
West Bengal	1,01,88,842
Jharkhand	44,36,052
Odisha	67,39,993
Chhattisgarh	50,91,832
Madhya Pradesh	1,21,92,267
Gujarat	68,39,415
Daman & Diu	772
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	17,799
Maharashtra	1,34,86,140
Andhra Pradesh	1,69,67,754
Karnataka	71,55,963
Goa	26,760
Lakshadweep	1,256
Kerala	13,22,850
Tamil Nadu	96,06,547
Pondicherry	68,391
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	4,781
India	14,43,33,690

<https://sansad.in/getFile/loksabhaquestions/annex/11/AU3930.pdf>

The table no. 1. provides data on the number of landless agricultural laborers in each state and union territory (UT) in India, based on the 2011 Census. According to the data, the top five states with the highest number of landless agricultural laborers are Uttar Pradesh with 1,99,39,223, Bihar with 1,83,45,649, Andhra Pradesh with 1,69,67,754, Maharashtra with 1,34,86,140 and Madhya Pradesh with 1,21,92,267. On the other hand, the states with the lowest number of landless agricultural laborers are Lakshadweep with 1,256, Daman & Diu with 772, Dadra & Nagar Haveli with 1,779, Andaman & Nicobar Islands with 4,781, and Chandigarh with 1,687. These numbers highlight the significant regional disparities in the number of landless agricultural laborers across India.

The data also reveals that the total number of landless agricultural laborers in India is 14,43,33,690, which is a significant proportion of the country's population. This highlights the need for effective policies and programs to address the issues faced by landless agricultural laborers and to improve their socio-economic status. Overall, the table provides a comprehensive picture of the number of landless agricultural laborers in each state and UT in India, highlighting the regional disparities and the need for targeted interventions to address the issues faced by this vulnerable group.

The district-wise number of the landless labourers of Maharashtra:

The table no. 2. provides information about the total number of households and landless laborers in various districts of Maharashtra.

Table No. 2: The district-wise number of the landless labourers in Maharashtra

Name of district	Total No. of Households	Total No. of landless labour
Nandurbar	292828	178948
Dhule	306860	137359
Jalgaon	643191	363073
Buldana	461842	208133
Akola	281629	138919
Washim	223258	105327
Amravati	450098	245791
Wardha	226126	95708
Nagpur	414168	196210
Bhandara	243526	102953
Gondiya	265214	114737
Gadchiroli	231066	96123
Chandrapur	397430	170715
Yavatmal	584064	318923
Nanded	488582	181943
Hingoli	202854	77136
Parbhani	261070	92891
Jalna	314270	92095
Aurangabad	449363	140099
Nashik	702961	255391
Thane	626009	196541
Raigad	453135	100872
Pune	751874	166217
Ahmadnagar	763339	200445
Bid	460613	135938
Latur	360602	141587
Osmanabad	294600	98028
Solapur	597623	188658
Satara	539808	104777
Ratnagiri	343088	66624
Sindhudurg	186826	37702
Kolhapur	590837	111462
Sangli	433206	88409
Total	13841960	4949734

https://rsdebate.nic.in/bitstream/123456789/697287/1/IQ_248_11022019_U862_p286_p288.pdf

The table no. 2. provides data on the total number of households and landless laborers in various districts of Maharashtra. In Maharashtra, the district of Nandurbar has 2,92,828 households and 1,78,948 landless laborers. Dhule has 3,06,860 households and 1,37,359 landless laborers. Jalgaon has 6,43,191 households and 3,63,073 landless laborers. Buldana has 4,61,842 households and 2,08,133 landless laborers. Akola has 2,81,629 households and 1,38,919 landless laborers. Washim has 2,23,258 households and 1,05,327 landless laborers. Amravati has 4,50,098 households and 2,45,791 landless laborers. Wardha has 2,26,126 households and 95,708 landless laborers. Nagpur has 4,14,168 households and 1,96,210 landless laborers. Bhandara has 2,43,526 households and 1,02,953 landless laborers. Gondiya has 2,65,214 households and 1,14,737 landless laborers. Gadchiroli has 2,31,066 households and 96,123 landless laborers. Chandrapur has 3,97,430 households and 1,70,715 landless laborers. Yavatmal has 584,064 households and

3,18,923 landless laborers. Nanded has 4,88,582 households and 1,81,943 landless laborers. Hingoli has 2,02,854 households and 77,136 landless laborers. Parbhani has 2,61,070 households and 92891 landless laborers. Jalna has 3,14,270 households and 92,095 landless laborers. Aurangabad has 4,49,363 households and 1,40,099 landless laborers. Nashik has 7,02,961 households and 2,55,391 landless laborers. Thane has 6,26,009 households and 1,96,541 landless laborers. Raigarh has 4,53,135 households and 1,00,872 landless laborers. Pune has 7,51,874 households and 1,66,217 landless laborers. Ahmadnagar has 7,63,339 households and 2,00,445 landless laborers. Bid has 4,60,613 households and 1,35,938 landless laborers. Latur has 3,60,602 households and 1,41,587 landless laborers. Osmanabad has 2,94,600 households and 98,028 landless laborers. Solapur has 5,97,623 households and 188658 landless laborers. Satara has 539808 households and 1,04,777 landless laborers. Ratnagiri has 343088 households and 66,624 landless laborers. Sindhudurg has 1,86,826 households and 37,702 landless laborers. Kolhapur has 5,90,837 households 1,11,462 landless laborers. Sangli has 4,33,206 households and 88,409 landless laborers.

Remedies to Hardship Landless Agricultural labor for Improvement:

A) Measures of Improve Economical Condition of Agricultural labor:

Abolition of bonded labour: Due to the practice of bonded labour, agricultural labourers in rural areas used to work as slaves of moneylenders and landlords for low wages. Moreover, the working hours and duration were long. Due to this, agricultural labourers were exploited. Therefore, bonded labour has been abolished in the society.

Land allocation to agricultural labourers: Allocating additional land to agricultural labourers, including government-owned land, land grant movement and maximum holding area, will help in raising their economic status. They will get the satisfaction of becoming land owners. This will help in increasing agricultural productivity.

Land allocation to agricultural labourers for houses: In rural areas, government-owned land in village stations should be given free of cost to agricultural labourers and loans should be provided to them at low interest rates to build houses.

Development of rural small and cottage industries: In the case of agricultural labourers, the problem of unemployment and underemployment is widespread in rural areas. Encouraging the creation of small and cottage industries in rural areas will help in improving the condition of these labourers.

Various work schemes: Various work schemes should be started by various government departments in rural areas to provide permanent work to agricultural labourers. Due to this, seasonal agricultural labourers can get permanent work.

Co-operative societies of labourers: If government and agricultural cooperative societies are formed, wages can be provided at the minimum wage rate.

B) Legal measures to improve the economic condition of agricultural labourers:

Minimum Wages Act (1948): According to this act, the government fixes the minimum wage of agricultural labourers and revises it. It announces wages for farm houses as well as organized agricultural labourers in rural areas as per the Minimum Wage Act.

Employees Provident Fund (1952): The Central Government implements this scheme for workers in some agricultural sectors. In India, it has been implemented for agricultural workers working in farmhouses, orchards, tea, rubber etc.

Trade Unions Act (1926): According to this act, agricultural workers have been given the right to form trade unions to unite for their rights and justice and have a provision for their registration.

Compensation Act (1923):

The Government of India can seek compensation for agricultural workers in case of injury, accident, disability and death due to mechanization in agriculture. It has provided compensation for agricultural workers such as tractor drivers, bullock ploughing workers etc.

Employees State Insurance Act (1948):

This scheme has been applied to the agricultural workers of public trusts, tea, rubber etc. workers.

In this way, legal and social provisions have been made to improve the economic condition of agricultural workers. Similarly, in order to provide other benefits to agricultural workers, financial programs like food for marginal and smallholder agricultural workers, training scheme for rural youth, integrated rural development program, employment assurance scheme, Jawahar Gram Samridhhi Yojana, Rashtriya Gram Rozgar Yojana have been started. Agricultural workers should get employment after the season and they should get perennial work. For this, schemes like Swarnajayanti Gram Swaroggar (SGSY), Sampoorna Gram Rozgar Yojana (SGRY), Pradhan Mantri Gramodaya Yojana (PMGY) and Pradhan Mantri Rozgar Yojana have been started.

The Central Government Schemes for Agricultural labor: The Central Government has also launched the Atal Pension Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana and Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana for all citizens especially targeting unorganised workers to provide them comprehensive social security. The number of workers availing the benefits under social security schemes.

Conclusion:

The number of Indian Landless Agricultural Laborers has increased in the last hundred years. This is because, in India, the decline of handicrafts and cottage industries, increase in rural population, low rate of employment generation in the industrial sector, and increasing use of capital-intensive techniques in industrialization have led to an increase in the number of agricultural labourers for employment. As the unemployment rate in India increased after independence, employment generation did not occur in the secondary and tertiary sectors to the same extent.

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